

AN ALTERNATIVE METHOD FOR SOLVING QUADRATIC EQUATIONS BASED ON THE SUM AND DIFFERENCE OF THE ROOTS

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ABSTRACT. In this article, we present an alternative and elementary method for solving quadratic equations, based on the sum and difference of the roots. The method is derived from classical identities, rigorously proven, and compared with traditional approaches, highlighting its didactic applications.

1. INTRODUCTION

Quadratic equations and functions are fundamental in Mathematics and also have applications in other fields such as Physics, Engineering, and Computer Science. Some of the most commonly used methods for solving these equations include the standard quadratic formula, completing the square, and factoring.

Since the 16th century, following the work of François Viète, it has been known that the roots of a quadratic equation satisfy simple relations involving their sum and product. These identities not only play a fundamental role in Algebra but also suggest that the internal structure of quadratic solutions can be exploited to develop alternative solution methods.

In this article, we present an alternative method for solving quadratic equations based on the sum and difference of their roots. The aim is to derive the method, illustrate its application through examples, and discuss its potential pedagogical use.

2. DERIVATIONS AND MATHEMATICAL PROOFS

2.1. The Standard Quadratic Formula. The standard quadratic formula can be derived as follows:

$$ax^2 + bx + c = 0$$

$$x^2 + \frac{b}{a}x + \frac{c}{a} = 0$$

$$x^2 + \frac{b}{a}x = -\frac{c}{a}$$

$$x^2 + \frac{b}{a}x + \left(\frac{b}{2a}\right)^2 = -\frac{c}{a} + \left(\frac{b}{2a}\right)^2$$

$$\left(x + \frac{b}{2a}\right)^2 = \frac{b^2}{4a^2} - \frac{c}{a}$$

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$$\left(x + \frac{b}{2a}\right)^2 = \frac{b^2 - 4ac}{4a^2}$$

$$x + \frac{b}{2a} = \pm \frac{\sqrt{b^2 - 4ac}}{2a}$$

$$x = -\frac{b}{2a} \pm \frac{\sqrt{b^2 - 4ac}}{2a}$$

$$x = \frac{-b \pm \sqrt{b^2 - 4ac}}{2a}$$

Taking into account $\Delta = b^2 - 4ac$:

$$x = \frac{-b \pm \sqrt{\Delta}}{2a}$$

2.2. Using the Four Basic Arithmetic Operations on the Roots of a Quadratic Equation.

2.2.1. Sum.

$$x_1 + x_2 = \frac{-b + \sqrt{b^2 - 4ac}}{2a} + \frac{-b - \sqrt{b^2 - 4ac}}{2a}$$

$$x_1 + x_2 = \frac{-2b}{2a}$$

$$x_1 + x_2 = -\frac{b}{a}$$

2.2.2. Product.

$$x_1x_2 = \left(\frac{-b + \sqrt{b^2 - 4ac}}{2a}\right) \left(\frac{-b - \sqrt{b^2 - 4ac}}{2a}\right)$$

$$x_1x_2 = \frac{(-b)^2 - (\sqrt{b^2 - 4ac})^2}{4a^2}$$

$$x_1x_2 = \frac{b^2 - (b^2 - 4ac)}{4a^2}$$

$$x_1x_2 = \frac{b^2 - b^2 + 4ac}{4a^2}$$

$$x_1x_2 = \frac{4ac}{4a^2}$$

$$x_1x_2 = \frac{ac}{a^2}$$

$$x_1x_2 = \frac{c}{a}$$

2.2.3. *Division.*

$$\frac{x_1}{x_2} = \left(\frac{-b + \sqrt{\Delta}}{2a} \right) \left(\frac{2a}{-b - \sqrt{\Delta}} \right)$$

$$\boxed{\frac{x_1}{x_2} = \frac{-b + \sqrt{\Delta}}{-b - \sqrt{\Delta}}}$$

2.2.4. *Subtraction.*

$$x_1 - x_2 = \frac{-b + \sqrt{\Delta}}{2a} - \left(\frac{-b - \sqrt{\Delta}}{2a} \right)$$

$$x_1 - x_2 = \frac{-b + \sqrt{\Delta}}{2a} + \frac{b + \sqrt{\Delta}}{2a}$$

$$x_1 - x_2 = \frac{-b + \sqrt{\Delta} + b + \sqrt{\Delta}}{2a}$$

$$x_1 - x_2 = \frac{2\sqrt{\Delta}}{2a}$$

$$\boxed{x_1 - x_2 = \frac{\sqrt{\Delta}}{a}}$$

2.3. The Alternative Quadratic Formula. The roots of a quadratic equation can be obtained through a system of equations that can be written as follows:

$$\begin{cases} x_1 + x_2 = -\frac{b}{a} \\ x_1 - x_2 = \frac{\sqrt{\Delta}}{a} \end{cases}$$

Or

$$\begin{cases} x_1 + x_2 = S \\ x_1 - x_2 = D \end{cases}$$

Solving the system of equations above:

$$2x_1 = S + D$$

$$\boxed{x_1 = \frac{S + D}{2}}$$

$$\frac{S + D}{2} + x_2 = S$$

$$x_2 = S - \frac{S + D}{2}$$

$$x_2 = \frac{2S - S - D}{2}$$

$$\boxed{x_2 = \frac{S - D}{2}}$$

2.4. Constructing a Quadratic Equation from the Sum and Difference of Its Roots. The formula for the product of the roots can also be expressed in terms of sum and difference.

$$P = x_1x_2$$

$$P = \left(\frac{S+D}{2}\right)\left(\frac{S-D}{2}\right)$$

$$P = \frac{S^2 - D^2}{4}$$

To construct a quadratic equation from the sum and product of its roots, we use the formula:

$$x^2 - Sx + P = 0$$

We can also do this using the sum and the difference:

$$x^2 - Sx + \frac{S^2 - D^2}{4} = 0$$

2.5. Geometric Interpretation. The x -coordinate of the vertex is given by:

$$x_v = -\frac{b}{2a}$$

Or

$$x_v = \frac{S}{2}$$

The difference of the roots can be obtained from the formula of the vertex's y -coordinate. In fact, since:

$$y_v = -\frac{\Delta}{4a},$$

and

$$\Delta = a^2 \left(\frac{\sqrt{\Delta}}{a}\right)^2$$

It follows that:

$$y_v = \frac{-a^2 \left(\frac{\sqrt{\Delta}}{a}\right)^2}{4a}$$

$$y_v = \frac{-a^2 D^2}{4a}$$

$$y_v = \frac{-aD^2}{4}$$

The sum " S " of the roots represents twice the x -coordinate of the vertex, and the difference " D " corresponds to the distance along the x -axis between the two roots.

3. EXAMPLES

In this section, we present a systematic comparison between the standard quadratic formula and the alternative method based on the sum and difference of the roots.

3.1. Roots in the Natural Numbers.

Exemplo 3.1.

$$x^2 - 5x + 6 = 0.$$

$$\Delta = (-5)^2 - 4(1)(6)$$

$$\Delta = 25 - 24$$

$$\Delta = 1$$

$$x = \frac{5 \pm 1}{2}$$

$$\boxed{x_1 = 3} \quad \boxed{x_2 = 2}$$

Or

$$\begin{cases} x_1 + x_2 = 5 \\ x_1 - x_2 = 1 \end{cases}$$

$$2x_1 = 6 \quad x_2 = 5 - 3$$

$$\boxed{x_1 = 3} \quad \boxed{x_2 = 2}$$

3.2. Roots in the Integers.

Exemplo 3.2.

$$x^2 + x - 20 = 0,$$

$$\Delta = (1)^2 - 4(1)(-20)$$

$$\Delta = 1 + 80$$

$$\Delta = 81$$

$$x = \frac{-1 \pm 9}{2}$$

$$\boxed{x_1 = 4} \quad \boxed{x_2 = -5}$$

Or

$$\begin{cases} x_1 + x_2 = -1 \\ x_1 - x_2 = 9 \end{cases}$$

$$2x_1 = 8 \quad x_2 = -1 - 4$$

$$\boxed{x_1 = 4}$$

$$\boxed{x_2 = -5}$$

3.3. Rational but Non-integer Roots.

Exemplo 3.3.

$$4x^2 - 8x + 3 = 0.$$

$$\Delta = (-8)^2 - 4(4)(3)$$

$$\Delta = 64 - 48$$

$$\Delta = 16$$

$$x = \frac{8 \pm 4}{8}$$

$$\boxed{x_1 = \frac{3}{2}}$$

$$\boxed{x_2 = \frac{1}{2}}$$

Or

$$\begin{cases} x_1 + x_2 = 2 \\ x_1 - x_2 = 1 \end{cases}$$

$$2x_1 = 3 \quad x_2 = 2 - \frac{3}{2}$$

$$\boxed{x_1 = \frac{3}{2}}$$

$$\boxed{x_2 = \frac{1}{2}}$$

3.4. Irrational Real Roots.

Exemplo 3.4.

$$x^2 - 3x + 1 = 0$$

$$\Delta = (-3)^2 - 4(1)(1)$$

$$\Delta = 9 - 4$$

$$\Delta = 5$$

$$x = \frac{3 \pm \sqrt{5}}{2}.$$

$$\boxed{x_1 = \frac{3 + \sqrt{5}}{2}}$$

$$\boxed{x_2 = \frac{3 - \sqrt{5}}{2}}$$

Or

$$\begin{cases} x_1 + x_2 = 3 \\ x_1 - x_2 = \sqrt{5} \end{cases}$$

$$2x_1 = 3 + \sqrt{5} \quad x_2 = 3 - \frac{3 - \sqrt{5}}{2}$$

$$\boxed{x_1 = \frac{3 + \sqrt{5}}{2}}$$

$$\boxed{x_2 = \frac{3 - \sqrt{5}}{2}}$$

3.5. Real Double Root.

Exemplo 3.5.

$$x^2 - 2x + 1 = 0.$$

$$\Delta = (-2)^2 - 4(1)(1)$$

$$\Delta = 4 - 4$$

$$\Delta = 0$$

$$x = \frac{2 \pm \sqrt{0}}{2}.$$

$$\boxed{x = 1}$$

Or

$$\begin{cases} x_1 + x_2 = 2 \\ x_1 - x_2 = 0 \end{cases}$$

$$2x_1 = 2 \quad x_2 = 2 - 1$$

$$\boxed{x_1 = 1}$$

$$\boxed{x_2 = 1}$$

3.6. Non-real Complex Roots.

Exemplo 3.6.

$$x^2 - 4x + 13 = 0$$

$$\Delta = (-4)^2 - 4(1)(13)$$

$$\Delta = 16 - 52$$

$$\Delta = -36$$

$$x = \frac{4 \pm \sqrt{-36}}{2}.$$

$$x = \frac{4 \pm 6i}{2}.$$

$$x = 2 \pm 3i.$$

$$\boxed{x_1 = 2 + 3i} \quad \boxed{x_2 = 2 - 3i}$$

Or

$$\begin{cases} x_1 + x_2 = 4 \\ x_1 - x_2 = 6i \end{cases}$$

$$2x_1 = 4 + 6i \quad x_2 = 4 - 2 - 3i$$

$$\boxed{x_1 = 2 + 3i} \quad \boxed{x_2 = 2 - 3i}$$

4. DISCUSSION

The standard quadratic formula is the one most commonly used in traditional education, but we have seen that a quadratic equation can be solved in other ways that are equally valid and insightful. In many cases, formulas are merely memorized rather than understood through their derivation. If logical reasoning, curiosity, and creativity were more strongly encouraged, we could achieve significant advances in all fields of science. It is possible that some of the equations presented here have appeared previously in lesser-known scientific works. However, the primary goal of this article is to provide an original approach and derivation, emphasizing the practical applications, particularly in the teaching and learning of Mathematics.

5. CONCLUSION

This article presented an alternative method for solving quadratic equations with potential applications in education and scientific outreach.

We have seen that the method can be extended and refined. I hope that this work may serve as a foundation for future research.

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